

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG
emission estimates

Tracing air masses via radon

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Post 1

How does radon tell us about how air moves and mixes?

Radon is a naturally occurring radioactive gas. It originates nearly completely from land because it is created by the decay of naturally occurring radium in rocks and soils. As there is very little radium in suspended ocean sediments, not much radon comes from the oceans.

As a gas, radon mixes with the air and is moved by wind. It has a half-life of about 3.8 days, so after 3.8 days half of the radon that came out of the ground will have disappeared. After 2 or 3 weeks, there is almost none left at all!

Together, these two properties mean that by just measuring radon, we can get some very interesting information about the air: mainly, in the past few weeks, how long has this particular bit of air spent over land. Since most sources of pollution are also on land, just measuring the radon in air at remote sites in the ocean can tell us how likely it is that the air contains other pollution. Or how long the air has been away from any large pollution sources and is behaving like “background” air.

In NuClim, we will use the radon concentration in the air measured at ARM User Facility ENA station Graciosa and ICOS station Mace Head to characterise how much the air reaching the stations has been recently influenced by land, or whether it has spent a long time just over the ocean. Air that has only been over the Atlantic Ocean for more than two weeks can help to tell us the background concentrations of greenhouse gases in air arriving in Europe, and therefore offer important information for research, regulation and monitoring.

Post 2

Radon (Rn) is a naturally occurring radioactive gas. It is created by the radioactive decay of radium (Ra) in rocks and soil which itself ultimately originates from uranium (U). Radon decays to polonium (Po) and, in the end, to lead (Pb).

Radon is the first (and only) gas in the uranium decay chain. As such it might dissipate freely into the atmosphere. However, the products of its decay are solids, which attach to other particles in the atmosphere and settle to the ground eventually.

Many isotopes of radon occur naturally. In our study, we focus on radon-222 which has a half-life of about 3.8 days. The other two isotopes of radon (radon-219 and radon-220) relevant in atmospheric research have much shorter half-lives (less than a minute). They are, therefore, not relevant in our context of determining air mass movement over several days to weeks.

